

ON THE COMPOSITION AND CONSTITUTION OF PARAMOLYBDATES.

BY PRIYADARANJAN RAY AND SUSHIL KUMAR SIDDHANTA.

According to some workers the paramolybdates have the composition, $3R_2O \cdot 7MoO_3$ aq., and should be formulated as $R_6Mo_7O_{24}$ aq., while others represent them as $5R_2O \cdot 12MoO_3$ aq., or more definitely as $R_5H_5[Mo_7O_{24}]^{6-}$ aq., due to Rosenheim. Jander in agreement with the latter view, represents the paramolybdate as $R_5[HM_6O_{21}]^{4-}$ aq.

With a view to a critical examination of the problem, the following paramolybdates of complex metallic biguanide ions of high equivalent weight were prepared and their properties studied :

The results are in good accord with the older formula, $3R_2O \cdot 7MoO_3$ aq., showing that the paramolybdate ion is best represented as $[Mo_7O_{24}]^{6-}$. The conclusion is based mainly upon the analytical composition of the compounds, their dehydration, followed by rehydration, and other general chemical properties

The composition of the paramolybdates has been a subject of long-standing controversy. One school of workers, Lotz (*Annalen*, 1854, 91, 49), Delafontaine (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1865, 95, 136) and Ullik (*Annalen*, 1867, 144, 204; 1870, 183, 373) found the analytical values to correspond to the composition, $3R_2O \cdot 7MoO_3$ aq. (R = a univalent metal atom). Later Klason assigned the composition, $5R_2O \cdot 12MoO_3$ aq., to this class of compounds (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 153). The ratios of Mo : R in these two formulae are fairly close, being 1.167 and 1.20 respectively; it is, therefore, difficult to ascertain which of the two formulae is correct. Junius (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 46, 428) on the basis of analysis of barium and thallium paramolybdates, approved of the composition, $5R_2O \cdot 12MoO_3$ aq., and this was confirmed by Wempe (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1912, 78, 298) and Rosenheim (*ibid.*, 1916, 96, 139). On the other hand, Barbieri (*Atti. R. Acad. Lincei*, 1908, 171, 540; 1911, 201, 18) prepared a few mixed rare earth ammonium paramolybdates to which the formula, $M(NH_4)_2Mo_7O_{24}$ aq., can be assigned (M = La, Ce, Pr, Nd or Sm). Copeaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 156, 1771) suggested the constitution, $R_5[Mo(Mo_2O_7)_2O_3]$, for the paramolybdates from a study of their dehydration by heat and their absorption of ultraviolet light. Travers and Malaparade (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1926, 39, 1543) from the titration values of sodium and potassium paramolybdates with alkali,

concluded that the ordinary ammonium paramolybdate constitutes mixed crystals of 10% trimolybdate with 90% Delafontaine's paramolybdate, $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 9\text{aq}$.

Jander and his co-workers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 180, 129; 1930, 187, 60; 1933, 211, 49; 1933, 212, 1; 1934, 217, 65) from a detailed study of ionic diffusion in presence of an inert electrolyte, determined the masses of various polymolybdate ions, produced by the gradual addition of acids to a solution of normal molybdate. The values, thus obtained, were further supported by the results of conductometric titration of normal sodium molybdate by nitric acid, as well as by those of thermometric titration and also by a study of the absorption spectra of an increasingly acidified solution of a normal molybdate. The formula, thus suggested for the paramolybdate by Jander, is represented as $\text{Na}_5[\text{HMo}_6\text{O}_{21}] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which resembles more or less closely that advocated by Rosenheim (*loc. cit.*), $\text{Na}_5\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6] \cdot 15\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, based on Werner's co-ordination theory.

Brintzinger and Ratanarat (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1935, 224, 97) also from a measurement of the rate of electro dialysis, determined the ionic weight of polymolybdates. Their values were mostly found to be in good accord with those of Jander.

Recently Garielli and Tettamanzi (*Gazzetta*, 1935, 65, 1009) have prepared the mixed paramolybdates of ammonium and triethanolamine and represented them by the following formulæ: (1) $(\text{TmH})(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (2) $(\text{TmH})_2(\text{NH}_4)_4\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (3) $(\text{TmH})_3(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{Tm} = \text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{OH})_3$, one molecule of triethanolamine. The authors showed that the compound No. 3, for instance, represented on Rosenheim's scheme, assumes the formula (c) :— $(\text{TmH})_3(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6]$ with N, 4·81; NH_3 , 2·34; Mo, 39·64 per cent., in which the ratio $\text{Tm}:\text{Mo}$ becomes 0·500 and $\text{NH}_4:\text{Mo}$ as 0·333. The ratios actually found, however, approximate to 0·429 and 0·429 respectively in agreement with formula (3) assigned by them. But this is not very convincing, since the compounds can easily be represented as double salts maintaining Rosenheim's formulation. The compound (3), for instance, can be represented as:—

(a) $(\text{TmH})_3\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6], (\text{NH}_4)_3\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6]$, with ratio $\text{Tm}:\text{Mo} = 0\cdot 417$ and $\text{NH}_4:\text{Mo} = 0\cdot 417$, or even as (b) $(\text{TmH})_3(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6], (\text{NH}_4)_3\text{MoO}_4$ with ratio $\text{Tm}:\text{Mo} = 0\cdot 429$ and $\text{NH}_4:\text{Mo} = 0\cdot 429$. These ratios are either identical or very close to those actually found. Besides, there is no difference between the percentage values for formulæ (3) and (b) the values found by the authors are such as does not permit a definite choice between (3) and (a). This is evident from the following figures: Formulæ (3) and (b): N, 5·15; NH_3 , 3·12; Mo, 41·16 per cent. Formula (a):

N, 5'05; NH₃, 3'06; Mo, 41'53 per cent. Expt. values (authors') : N, 5'21; NH₃, 2'90, 3'24; Mo, 40'79, 41'22 per cent.

It might also be pointed out that the methods of preparing the compounds by the addition of a base is likely to raise the p_n value of the solution leading to the formation of normal molybdate which then combines to a double salt as in (b).

The formulae of (2) and (x) may similarly be represented as

Sturdivant (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 630) from X-ray measurements has determined the molecular weight of ammonium paramolybdate which is found to agree with the formula $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and not with $(\text{NH}_4)_5\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6]$, suggested by Rosenheim.

It was expected that the paramolybdates of polyvalent complex cations of large ionic weight like those of

prepared and studied, might throw some light on this vexed problem. Experiments with this end in view have led to the isolation of mixed paramolybdates of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{BigH})_2]_2 \text{R}_2\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where R=Na or NH₄, and the pure complex paramolybdates of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$

The theoretical percentage of the constituent elements in the above four paramolybdates as required by the older formula, Rosenheim's formula and Jander's formula are summarised in Table I along with the analytical results.

An examination of Table I would show that the analytical composition of all the compounds described therein, particularly those of the mixed paramolybdates, correspond more closely to the older formula, $\text{R}_2\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot \text{aq.}$, than to Rosenheim's formula, $\text{R}_2\text{H}_5[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6] \cdot \text{aq.}$ or Jander's formula, $\text{R}_3[\text{HMo}_6\text{O}_{21}] \cdot \text{aq.}$ It might, of course, be suggested that the mixed paramolybdates can as well be represented as double salts on the basis of Rosenheim's formula, so as to correspond approximately to the analytical results, as shown below :

TABLE I.

Compounds.	Represented on the older formula.	Represented on the Rosenheim's formula.	Represented on the Jander's formula.	As double salt with Rosenheim's or Jander's formula.	Analytical results found.
1. Cobaltic tris-bisguanide paramolybdate (hydrated) (A)	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2\text{Mo}^+\text{O}_4 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 21.64; Co, 6.07; Mo, 34.69; H_2O , 83.34%.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2\text{H}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_9$ O_4 requires:— N, 21.70; Co, 5.92; Mo, 34.69; H_2O , 86.66%.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ $6.33\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 21.48; Co, 6.03; Mo, 35.34; H_2O , 6.87%.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ $6.33\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 21.48; Co, 6.03; Mo, 35.34; H_2O , 6.87%.	N, 21.54, 21.48; Co, 6.10, 6.05, 6.10; Mo, 33.53, 34.57, 34.70, 34.64, 34.70; H_2O , 8.28, 8.25, 8.48, 8.19%.
2. Cobaltic tris-bisguanide paramolybdate (anhydrous).	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2\text{Mo}^+\text{O}_4$ requires:— Mo, 37.76%.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2\text{H}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ requires:— N, 19.52; Ni, 7.80; Mo, 38.25; $\text{NiO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 67.25%.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BiG}H_3)_3]_2[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ requires:— Mo, 38.00%.		Mo, 37.67%.
3. Nickel bisguanide ammonium paramolybdate. (B)	$[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Mo}^+\text{O}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 28.26; Ni, 6.97; Mo, 39.88; $\text{NiO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 68.66%.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{H}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ requires:— N, 19.52; Ni, 7.80; Mo, 38.25; $\text{NiO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 67.25%.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2\text{NH}_4[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 19.52; Ni, 7.80; Mo, 38.25; $\text{NiO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 67.25%.	D(R) or D(J) requires:— N, 27.92; Ni, 6.86; Mo, 39.77; $\text{NiO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 69.05%.	N, 28.39; Ni, 7.03, 7.0; Mo, 39.77; $\text{NiO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 68.66%.
4. Nickel bisguanide sodium paramolybdate. (C)	$[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mo}^+\text{O}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— Ni, 6.93; Mo, 39.95; Na, 2.71%.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2\text{NaH}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ requires:— Ni, 7.77; Mo, 38.12; Na, 1.52%.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2\text{Na}[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— Ni, 7.77; Mo, 38.12; Na, 1.52%.	D(R) or D(J) requires:— Ni, 6.82; Mo, 40.6; Na, 2.64%.	Ni, 6.92; Mo, 39.41; Na, 2.64%.
5. Copper bisguanide paramolybdate. (D)	$[\text{Cu}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2\text{Mo}^+\text{O}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 21.83; Cu, 9.03; Mo, 34.91; $\text{CuO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 64.77%.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2\text{H}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ requires:— N, 21.47; Cu, 9.74; Mo, 35.31; $\text{CuO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 64.51%.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires:— N, 21.47; Cu, 9.74; Mo, 35.31; $\text{CuO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 64.51%.		N, 21.63; Cu, 9.95; Mo, 34.87; $\text{CuO} + \text{MoO}_3$, 64.63%.

D(R) = Double salt with Rosenheim's formula:—
 $[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2[\text{H}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]_2 \text{R}_2\text{H}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4[\text{MoO}_4]_2$
 D(J) = Double salt with Jander's formula:—
 $[\text{Ni}(\text{BiG}H_3)_2]_2[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2 \text{R}_2[\text{H}(\text{HMo}^+\text{O}_2)]_2$ where R = NH_4 or Na.

The representation (i) is untenable as there is no reason why a normal molybdate should be formed in the mixture. Nothing very definitely can be stated against the representation (ii) simply from analytical results, though there is still appreciable difference in the percentage values of Ni, Mo and specially of nitrogen. The nickel biguanide paramolybdate has been obtained in a rather impure state by adding a dilute solution of ammonium paramolybdate, drop by drop, to that of an excess of concentrated solution of nickel biguanide hydrochloride.

On the basis of Rosenheim's scheme of representation, the paramolybdates contain 3.5 molecules of "water of constitution" for every 6 Mo-atoms or 4 molecules for every 7 Mo-atoms. According to the older formula, on the other hand, all the water molecules should behave as "water of crystallisation."

Table II summarises the results of dehydration of the metal biguanide paramolybdates discussed above, before any decomposition sets in, and also of the rehydration of the dehydrated products on keeping the latter exposed to air at the room temperature.

The cobaltic *trisbiguanide* paramolybdate thus loses $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, *i.e.*, 6.4% of its weight even at 80° ; on the basis of Rosenheim's formula, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]_3/3\text{H}_6[\text{H}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_6]$, $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, it should have lost only 5.42% of its weight by the removal of all its water of crystallisation ($5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) without decomposition. Besides, the loss of all the water molecules from the compound at 110° without decomposition definitely invalidates Rosenheim's representation. Table II also shows that the compound regains at the ordinary temperature the whole of its water lost during heating without any change of its original properties.

For the same reason the compounds 2, 3, and 4 in Table II should not have lost any water at 70° without decomposition according to Rosenheim's scheme; all these compounds, however, lose a part of their water at this temperature, and regain it back on subsequent exposure to air at the room temperature. No positive evidence regarding their decomposition on dehydration could, however, be obtained.

The dehydration experiments alone cannot, however, rule out Jander's formula for paramolybdates, but when coupled with the analytical results as given above, they furnish evidences against the validity of the latter.

From the considerations set forth above, it may be concluded that the composition of the paramolybdate ion is best represented by $(\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24})^{6-}$, as assumed in the older formula.

TABLE II.

Compounds	Loss of H ₂ O in mol. at					H ₂ O regained
	60°.	70°.	80°.	100°.	110°.	
1. Cobaltic trisbiguanide paramolybdate [Co (BigH) ₃] ₂ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .9H ₂ O	3'75	4'75	7'0	8'0	9'0	9'0 mol.
2. Nickel biguanide ammonium paramolybdate [Ni (BigH) ₂] ₂ (NH ₄) ₂ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	1'0	1'63	1'63	1'63	...	1'60
3. Nickel biguanide sodium paramolybdate [Ni (BigH) ₂] ₂ Na ₂ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	...	1'75	1'75	1'75	1'75	1'75
4. Copper biguanide paramolybdate [Cu (BigH) ₂] ₂ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	...	2'17	2'50	3'0	3'0	3'0

The Constitution and the Structure of Paramolybdate Ion.

Copeaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 186, 1771), as the result of several dehydration experiments and a study of light absorption in ultraviolet region, concluded that the paramolybdates should be formulated as R₃[Mo(Mo₂O₇)₃O₂]⁻aq.

Travers and Malaparade (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1926, 39, 1543), however, from a study of the colour reactions with potassium ferrocyanide assumed that the paramolybdate ion, (Mo₇O₂₄)⁶⁻, dissociates in solution to give the metamolybdate and the normal molybdate ions with the establishment of the following equilibrium, the relative proportion of each depending on the concentration of the solution as shown below :

[gives colour reaction with ferrocyanide].

According to these authors the metamolybdate ion is represented by (Mo₄O₁₃)²⁻.

It has, however, been observed that both cobaltic biguanide metamolybdate and cobaltic biguanide paramolybdate are almost equally insoluble in water, while cobaltic biguanide normal molybdate is quite soluble. If any equilibrium like (1) and (2) existed in solutions of paramolybdates,

one could have scarcely expected to obtain, by adding cobaltic biguanide chloride or hydroxide to a concentrated solution of ammonium paramolybdate, a pure cobaltic biguanide paramolybdate as a precipitate without any contamination with metamolybdate, as the latter ion is supposed to abound in concentrated solutions of paramolybdate. But, as a matter of fact, pure cobaltic biguanide paramolybdate has been obtained both from the strong and dilute solutions of ammonium paramolybdate. The paramolybdate ion should, therefore, be regarded as a discrete entity by itself without any dissociation into the meta and normal molybdate ions in aqueous solution, as suggested by the above mentioned authors.

A consideration of the ionic radius ratio of Mo^{6+} and O^{2-} ions on the basis of Goldschmidt's view (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 29, 253) by Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2868) and Keggin (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, A144, 75), and a study by X-ray measurement of heteropoly acids by Illingworth and Keggin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 575) as well as by others have led to the conclusion that the polymolybdate ion in general is made up of (MoO_6) -octahedral units by sharing corners or edges. It has, indeed, been suggested by Anderson (*Nature*, 1937, 140, 850) that in the paramolybdate ion, $(\text{Mo}_6\text{O}_{24})^{6-}$, there are six MoO_6 -octahedra linked together in a hexagonal annulus, each sharing two corners with the neighbouring octahedra, and the central cavity is filled up by the remaining Mo atom with the same six-fold octahedral co-ordination with the surrounding O-atoms (*cf.* also Emeleus and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", G. Routledge and Sons, Ltd., p. 194). However, this structure does not satisfy the electrostatic valency principle of Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1010) and should be regarded as rather speculative. For the present we should, therefore, remain satisfied with the simple chemical representation of the paramolybdate ion as a Werner complex of the type $[\text{Mo}(\text{MoO}_4)_6]^{6-}$ without attempting any detailed geometrical arrangement.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Paramolybdate (A).—A dilute solution (3 g. in 200 c.c.) of cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride (Rây and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 621) was added, drop by drop with stirring, to a concentrated solution (5 g. in 30 c.c.) of ammonium paramolybdate. A dull red precipitate separated at once even by the addition of the first drop of the complex hydrochloride solution. The mixture was heated at $80^\circ\text{--}90^\circ$ on the water-bath for a few minutes. The precipitate was then filtered hot,

washed several times first with hot water and then with alcohol. The product was dried in air.

The ammonium paramolybdate, used in this experiment, was obtained by recrystallising Merck's extra pure product from slightly ammoniacal solution. [Found: Mo, 54.39. $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mo, 54.36 per cent].

The same compound was also prepared by adding a dilute solution (2.5 g. in 300 c.c.) of ammonium paramolybdate, drop by drop with stirring, to an excess of complex cobaltic salt solution (2 g. in 15 c.c.).

The substance formed dull red microcrystalline powder, insoluble in water or alcohol, but readily soluble in acids or ammonia.

For analysis and composition see Table I.

Dehydration.

Weight of the substance = 2.6405 g.

Temp.	60°	70°	80°	100°	110°
Loss of wt. (g.)	0.0917	0.1172	0.1690	0.1934	0.2190
Loss of H ₂ O (mol.)	3.75	4.79	6.91	7.91	8.95

H₂O (total) = 8.28% of the hydrated compound.

The whole of this water was regained after some days on keeping the dehydrated product exposed to air at the room temperature.

On adding cobaltic biguanide chloride solution to that of a normal sodium molybdate no precipitate was obtained. This shows that the cobaltic biguanide normal molybdate is soluble. The solubility of the cobaltic biguanide paramolybdate in ammonia or an excess of cobaltic biguanide hydroxide solution is evidently due to the formation of this soluble normal molybdate under the influence of alkali. The same compound could be obtained even by adding an 1% solution of cobaltic biguanide dihydrate (Ray and Dutt, *loc. cit.*), drop by drop with stirring, to a concentrated solution of ammonium paramolybdate at 50°-60°.

Nickel Biguanide Ammonium Paramolybdate (B).—A dilute solution (2 g. in 250 c.c.) of nickel biguanide hydrochloride (Ray and Purakayastha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 217) was added, drop by drop with stirring, to a concentrated solution (3 g. in 20 c.c.) of ammonium paramolybdate. An immediate precipitation occurred. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for a few minutes, filtered hot and was washed several times first with hot water and then with alcohol. The precipitate was finally dried in air.

The substance forms a yellow microcrystalline powder, sparingly soluble in cold water and insoluble in alcohol. On boiling with sodium carbonate solution it liberated ammonia.

For analysis and composition see Table I.

Dehydration.

Weight of the substance = 0.9793 g.

Temp.	...	60°	70°	80°	100°
Loss of H ₂ O (g.)	...	0.0096	0.0166	0.0167	0.0170
Loss of H ₂ O (mol.)	...	0.02	1.63	1.63	1.63

The whole of water lost by heating was regained on keeping the product at the room temperature, exposed to air for some days.

Nickel Biguanide Paramolybdate.—On adding a dilute solution of ammonium paramolybdate to a concentrated solution of nickel biguanide hydrochloride a yellow microcrystalline precipitate was obtained, which, on analysis, proved to be nickel biguanide paramolybdate in a rather impure state. {Found: Ni, 9.29, 9.34; Mo, 32.99, 33.0. [Ni (BigH₂)₃Mo₇O₂₄.4H₂O requires Ni, 9.25; Mo, 35.10 per cent]. On shaking with an excess of ammonium paramolybdate solution for a long time it tends to change into the above described mixed salt.

Nickel Biguanide Sodium Paramolybdate (C).—The substance separated immediately as a yellow precipitate by adding, drop by drop with stirring, a dilute solution (1 g. in 200 c.c.) of nickel biguanide hydrochloride to a concentrated solution (3 g. in 15 c.c.) of sodium paramolybdate at 60°–70°. The mixture was kept on the water-bath for some time. The precipitate was then filtered hot, washed and dried as in the previous case.

Sodium paramolybdate was obtained by dissolving 1 mol. of MoO₃ (27 g.) in a solution containing 1 mol. of NaOH (7.5 g.); the solution was evaporated on the water-bath to a small volume, when sodium paramolybdate crystallised out on keeping. (Found: Mo, 46.35. Calc. for Na₆Mo₇O₂₄.14H₂O: Mo, 46.46 per cent).

For analysis and composition see Table I.

Dehydration.

Weight of the substance = 1.1323 g.

Temp.	...	70°	80°	100°	110°
Loss of H ₂ O (g.)	...	0.0204	0.0204	0.0211	0.0212
Loss of H ₂ O (mol.)	...	1.7	1.7	1.76	1.76

The product on exposure to air at the room temperature for some days regained its original weight.

Copper Biguanide Paramolybdate (D).—A solution (2.3 g. in 200 c.c.) of copper biguanide hydrochloride (Rây and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 617) was added, drop by drop with stirring, to a solution (2.6 g. in 20 c.c.) of ammonium paramolybdate. The mixture with the precipitate was then heated on the water-bath, filtered, washed and dried as already described. The substance forms a violet-red powder, sparingly soluble in hot water. For analysis and composition see Table I.

Dehydration.

Weight of the substance = 2.2123 g.

Temp.	.. 70°	80°	100°	110°
Loss of H ₂ O (g.)	... 0.0437	0.0535	0.0617	0.0629
Loss of H ₂ O (mol.)	... 2.11	2.59	3.04	3.04

The whole of the water, lost by heating, was regained on keeping the product exposed to air at the room temperature for some days.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received April 18, 1941